

Incidence of rice stem borers (SB) in Sind

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We surveyed SB in Jan 1988 and estimated tiller infestation and number of larvae in rice stubble in rice-growing areas of Sind.

Samples of rice stubbles were collected in 33 locations in Upper Sind and 20 in Lower Sind. Average tiller infestation was 19%.

Rice areas around Shikarpur, Jamra, Brohi, and Wagan in Upper Sind and around Thatta, Jatichok, Cularchi, Chandio, Telhar, and Sajawal in Lower Sind were severely infested (see figure).

Of larvae collected, only 2% were pink stem borer *Sesamia* spp.; the remainder were yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walk.) and white stem borer *S. innotata* (Walk.). ■

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Integrated pest management—weeds

First report of *Monochoria vaginalis* in Iran

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Monochoria vaginalis (Pontederiaceae) is a broadleaf weed distributed in Asia, Africa, and Oceania. Until now, it had not been found in Iran.

The main noxious weeds in transplanted rice in north Iran are *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Alisma plantago-aquatica*, and *Paspalum distichum*.

In Jul 1989, we collected samples of *M. vaginalis* from ricefields in Amlesh, the eastern part of Guilan Province (Fig. 1). Identification was confirmed by Dr. F. Termeh, Botanic Department of Plant Pests and Diseases Research Institute, P.O. Box 1454, Tehran.

The plant is a weed in ricefields and a new species for flora of Iran (Fig. 2). It is

also the first species of Pontederiaceae in Iran.

We found this weed in about 500 ha, where it has become the main noxious weed.

It was not known whether it is indigenous or exotic, and we are investigating its origin. ■

1. Area where *Monochoria vaginalis* is found in Iran.

2. *Monochoria vaginalis* in a farmer's field.